

AN OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF TNSTC EMPLOYEES (A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO POLLACHI BRANCH)

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Introduction:

In the fast changing world of today, no individual is free from stress and no profession is stress free. Everyone experiences stress, whether it is within the family, business, organization, study, work, or any other social or economical activity. Thus in modern time, stress in general and job stress in particular has become a part of the life and has received considerable attention in recent years. Stress has become the core concern in the life of everyone, but everybody wants stress-free life. Not only just high pressure executives are its key victims but it also includes laborers', slum dwellers, working women, businessmen, professionals and even children.

Key Words: Stress, Employees & Working Environment

Statement of the Problem:

Transport work has been identified as one of the most stressful profession today. The reasons for that may be more work load, government rules and regulations. Working environment has a pronounced effect on stress. Time management, traffic congestions, accident fear, overcrowd, passenger misbehavior etc., may also lead to stress. This study aims to investigate the experience of stress level among transport employees. The following questions were raised in the minds of the Researcher.

- ✓ What is the nature of working environment of transport employees and are they satisfied with the working time of the transport?
- ✓ What is the perception of employee on the existing working environment and are they really satisfied and are the factors that influence the level of satisfaction?
- ✓ What is then the level of stress of transport employees?
- ✓ What are the factors causing the level of stress?

Review of Literature:

Oreoluwa Akingunola and Oludele Adigun (2010) a research study was conducted aimed at determining the existence of stress in the Nigerian Banking Industry. A structured questionnaire was designed to collect information from both executives and none-executives of the Nigerian banking industry. However, the stress level is higher among the executive than the none executive. It was concluded that there exist high level of stress in the Nigerian Banking Industry which affect personal health significantly thereby requiring management action in implementing stress relieving measures.

L. S. Kang and R. S. Sandhu (2011) in their article said that stress is an individual's state of mind in an encounter of demanding situation or any constraint in the organization which s/he feels harmful or threatening for her/himself. Stress emerges from various energy seeping conditions in the working environment.

Pisanti et al. (2011) compared job characteristics, organizational conditions, distress and well-being of nurses from two nationalities. The other studies focused on different settings and categories of nurses (registered nurses and practical nurses working in hospitals and health care centres.

Anbhule Hemant Arjun (2013) supervisor's support and co-workers help are heavily affect the working environment. The main purpose of this study is to find out the relation between job satisfaction and job stress among the bus drivers of public transport department of Pune Municipal Corporation. The participants of the study consist of 390 bus drivers of public transport department of Pune Municipal Corporation. The result shows that there is significance relation between job satisfaction and job stress. The result also implies that supervisor's support regarding job performance is very important. The result also shows that coworkers help in solving job related & personal problem can become major factor for creation of job dissatisfaction.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the various factors causing stress among transport employees.
- ✓ To measure the impact of job stress and satisfaction level of employees working in TNSTC.
- ✓ To offer suggestions for removing the job stress among employees.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study: A Study with Special Reference to Pollachi Branches

Sampling Design: Researcher used descriptive research for studying the attitude of the employee.

Sampling Unit: The workers are working in various cater of position. Random sampling method is adopted to get insight about the study.

Nature and Source of Data:

The data needed for the study is both primary and secondary data. The primary will be collected through questionnaires and interviewing the respondents using the interview schedule in the Pollachi. Secondary data collected through Internet, magazines, journals and books from various concerning libraries and inputs from employees in Pollachi branches.

Sampling Size:

A total of 150 respondents in TNSTC employees exclusively (drivers and conductors) are taken as Sample.

Statistical Tools Used for the Study:

The study has been analyzed using the following statistical tools.

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ Weighted Average method
- ✓ Chi-square test

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is confined to transport corporation which are located in pollachi branch only. So the results cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The sample size may be small. Personal bias of the respondents might have crept while answering a few questions in the structured questionnaire.
- ✓ The period of the study is limited.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Table 1: describes the demographical Profile of the Respondents for the study. Out of 150 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (30%) of the respondents are between the Age group of 39-48, most (35%) of the respondents are up to School level, (57%) of the respondents are Married,(51%) of the respondents are Drivers, the monthly income of (34%) respondents between Rs.15001-Rs.20000,(55%) of the respondents are said that the work pressure affect to health and body, mostly (65%) of the respondents says that the labour union convey the issues to top management.

Table 1: Demographical Profile of the Respondents

Factors	No. of Respondents N=150	Percentage
Age		
18-28	33	22
29-38	32	21
39-48	44	30
49-58	41	27
Educational Qualification		
School level	52	35
College level	41	27
Diploma	35	23
Others	22	15
Marital Status		
Married	86	57
Unmarried	64	43
Type Of Job		
Driver	77	51
Conductor	73	49
Monthly Income		
Below - Rs.10000	24	16
Rs.10001Rs.15000	32	21
Rs.15001Rs.20000	51	34
Rs.20001&above	43	29
Work Pressure Affect To Health And Body		
Yes	67	45
No	83	55
Labour Union Convey The Issues To Top Management		
Yes	53	35
No	97	65
Time Spend On Work		
Very often	46	31

Often	32	21
Sometimes	34	23
Rarely	17	11
Very rarely	21	14

Chi-Square Analysis:

Table 2: Relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and impact of Demonetization

Calculated χ^2 Value	Table Value	D.F	Remarks
Age Vs Time Spend On Work			
10.3709	21.026	12	Not significant
Marital Status Vs Time Spend On Work			
20.414	15.507	8	Significant
Monthly Earnings Vs Time Spend On Work			
7.0873	21.026	12	Not significant
Age And Work Pressure Affect Health And Body			
5.9993	7.815	3	Not significant
Marital Status and Work Pressure Affect Health And Body			
3.7081	5.991	2	Not significant
Age and Work Pressure			
4.1395	12.592	6	Not significant

* Significant at 5% present level.

Summary of Findings:

- ✓ Majority of the respondents (30%) belong to the age group of 38 and 48 years.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents (35%) qualifications at school level.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents (57%) are married.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents (51%) are driver.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents (34%) monthly earnings are between Rs.15000-Rs.20000.
- ✓ Majority (41%) of the respondents suffer work pressure frequently.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are (31%) very often faced too much time spend on work.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The employees need periodic refreshment programme that are facing more stress in their job so that they can concentrate more in their job and it can reduce the accidents.
- ✓ The corporation wants to set up hospitals for their own employee's and their dependents in subsidies cost. It will give them more commitment and involvement in their jobs and it can useful to reduce their health problems including stress.
- ✓ In the case of recruitment and selection, more attention is to be made towards objective assessment of the skills of the employees. The skills of the employees should be evaluated without any bias and discrimination at the time of selection.
- ✓ The corporation needs to think about providing additional training to the drivers and conductors to reduce the stress.

Conclusion:

The study was done to find out the employee's stress and satisfaction level towards each factor like compensation, working environment, career growth, management support, level of stress, and job satisfaction. A well developed transport system has positive implications for access to health care, education and other basic needs. In the case of passenger road transport, meeting mobility requirements efficiently and addressing environmental and developmental concerns requires a great attention to the efficient human resource management.

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